

Nutritional status, nutrient intake and use of enzyme supplements in paediatric patients with Cystic Fibrosis; a European multicentre study with reference to current guidelines

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ABSTRACT

Background: The New European guidelines have established the most updated recommendations on nutrition and pancreatic enzyme replacement therapy (PERT) in CF. In the context of MyCyFAPP project - a European study in children with CF aimed at developing specific tools for improvement of self-management - the objective of the current study was to assess nutritional status, daily energy and macronutrient intake, and PERT dosing with reference to these new guidelines.

Methods: Cross sectional study in paediatric patients with CF from 6 European centres. SD-scores for weight-for-age (WFA), height-for-age (HFA) and body mass index-for-age (BMI) were obtained. Through a specific 4-day food and enzyme-dose record, energy and macronutrients intake and PERT-use (LU/g lipids) were automatically calculated by the MyCyFAPP system. Comparisons were made using linear regression models.

Results: The lowest quartiles for BMI and HFA were between 0 and -1SD in all the centres with no significant differences, and 33.5% of the patients had a SD-score < 0 for all three parameters. The minimum energy intake recommendation was not reached by 40% of the children and mean nutrients intake values were 14%, 51% and 34% of the total energy for protein, carbohydrates and lipids respectively. When assessed per centre, reported PERT doses were in the recommended range in only 13.8% to 46.6% of the patients; from 5.6% up to 82.7% of children were above the recommended doses and 3.3% to 75% were below.

Conclusion: Among the 6 centres, a large variability and inconsistency with new guidelines on nutrition and PERT-use was found. Our findings document the lack of a general criterion to adjust PERT and suggest the potential benefit of educational and self-managerial tools to ensure adherence to therapies, both for clinical staff and

families. They will be taken into account when developing these new tools during the next stages of MyCyFAPP Project.

KEYWORDS: Cystic Fibrosis, nutritional status, pancreatic insufficiency, PERT, nutritional requirements macronutrients, guidelines, paediatrics, self-management, telemedicine

ABBREVIATIONS

BMI: body mass index for age

CI: confidence interval

CF: Cystic Fibrosis

E/S: enzyme to substrate ratio

ECFS: European Cystic Fibrosis Society

ESPEN: European Society for Parenteral and Enteral Nutrition

ESPGHAN: European Society for Paediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology and Nutrition

FER: food and enzymes record

HFA: height for age

kcal: kilocalorie

LU: lipase units

mHealth: mobile health

PERT: pancreatic enzyme replacement therapy

PI: pancreatic insufficiency

PS: pancreatic sufficiency

SD: standard deviation

WFA: weight for age

1 1. INTRODUCTION

2 Antibiotics, physiotherapy and nutrition are considered the three pillars in the
3 treatment of Cystic Fibrosis (CF) according to the most recent standards of care ¹.
4 Whilst therapies for lung disease have been a continuous focus of research in recent
5 years ² less high-impact studies have addressed the improvement of the nutritional
6 and pancreas-related aspects.

7 The importance of a good nutritional status has clearly emerged over the last
8 few decades with its direct relationship to a better lung function and consequently a
9 better overall prognosis and survival ^{1,3}. Obtaining and keeping a good nutritional
10 status is, however, a challenge in most patients with CF. This has several reasons,
11 i.e. the increased energy requirements secondary to chronic inflammation and
12 pancreatic insufficiency (PI) (present in almost 80% of patients) on one side and the
13 decreased energy intake and loss of nutrients due to maldigestion and
14 malabsorption on the other side ⁴.

15 Therefore, the main nutritional goal in children with CF is to avoid inadequate
16 nutrient intake and to follow a normal growth pattern according to age. Nutritional
17 follow-up and intervention is essential and should aim at achieving an optimal
18 adjustment of pancreatic enzyme replacement therapy (PERT) to correct pancreatic
19 insufficiency as well as at prescribing a balanced diet according to nutritional needs
20 ^{5,6}. The recently published guidelines on nutrition care for infants, children and adults
21 with CF compile the most recent scientific evidence and establish recommendations
22 regarding nutritional goals and PERT dosage ⁷.

23 In comparison with antibiotics or physiotherapy treatments, nutrition and
24 PERT are more likely to be mainly managed by the patients or parents themselves,
25 outside the care of the CF team. Eating and drinking is a daily need and patients are

26 supposed to comply with a balanced diet and adjust the dose of enzymes
27 accordingly. However, if an incorrect nutritional behaviour or an inadequate enzyme
28 dosage occurs, it will most likely not be detected and corrected until the next contact
29 or visit to the CF centre. Consequently, one of the ultimate goals of the medical care
30 in CF – achieving and maintaining an adequate nutritional status – will be
31 jeopardised rather than potentiated.

32 Therefore, nutritional education and treatment in CF can be considered as
33 one of the ideal targets of mobile health (mHealth) and patients' self-management.
34 These concepts have been pointed out as main priorities in the current European
35 Union's research and innovation programme, Horizon 2020. They strongly suggest
36 that the current and future lines of medical investigation should be focused on this
37 area ⁸.

38 In this scenario, MyCyFAPP Project (www.mycyfapp.eu) came to fruition as
39 an innovative approach towards the self-management of nutrition and PERT in
40 paediatric patients with CF by means of a mobile APP. The whole project includes
41 various studies in order to generate educational resources and supporting tools
42 addressed to patients, to ultimately achieve the overall goal.

43 The present study was carried out to obtain baseline information about
44 nutrient and PERT intake and identify possible discrepancies with the current
45 recommendations. This information will help to develop CF-specific, tailored
46 evidence-based tools to allow for the self-management of nutrition and PERT in
47 order to facilitate adherence to current recommendations. We therefore assessed
48 nutritional status, daily energy and macronutrient intake, and enzyme dosing of a
49 European population of children with CF and related these findings to the new
50 ESPGHAN/ECFS/ESPEN nutritional guidelines ⁷.

51

52 **2. METHODS**

53 **2.1. Subjects and Study design**

54 Patients with CF considered for enrolment in this cross-sectional study were
55 regularly followed in the 6 MyCyFAPP participating European CF Centres: Lisbon
56 (Portugal), Madrid (Spain), Valencia (Spain), Milan (Italy), Leuven (Belgium) and
57 Rotterdam (The Netherlands). Inclusion criteria required a confirmed diagnosis of CF
58 for at least 6 months and age between 1.0 to 17.9 years. Patients who had
59 undergone organ transplantation were excluded. Presence of pancreatic sufficiency
60 (PS) was not considered an exclusion criterion.

61 The anthropometric measurements were taken and clinical data registered.
62 Prospectively, participants completed a newly developed 4-day food and pancreatic
63 enzymes record. The collected information was securely stored in the online
64 MyCyFAPP project system, allowing for data storage and automatic calculations.
65 Participants followed their usual diet and took their regular enzyme dose as
66 prescribed by the specialists in their centres.

67 The study protocol was approved by the ethical committee of each CF centre
68 and conducted according to the Declaration of Helsinki guidelines. All parents and
69 patients were informed about the purpose and ultimate aim of the study and were
70 asked to sign the informed consent.

71

72 **2.2. Clinical and anthropometric data**

73 The anthropometric data were obtained by trained personnel of the CF
74 centres. After calibration of the equipment, weight was measured using a digital
75 scale to the nearest 0.1 kg and height was obtained with either a measuring board

76 (supine length) or stadiometer (standing height). Body mass index was calculated as
77 weight (kg) / height (m²). Anthropometric measurements were converted to standard
78 deviations scores e.g. “height for age” (HFA), “weight for age” (WFA), and “body
79 mass index for age” (BMI) using the CDC references ⁹.

80

81 **2.3. Nutritional data collection and calculation**

82 The specific 4 days food and enzymes record form (FER) was developed,
83 based on current recommendation that a 3 to 5 day diet record is necessary for a
84 quantitative evaluation of nutrient intake ⁷. The FER was structured in six sections: 3
85 main meals (breakfast, lunch and dinner) and 3 snacks (morning, afternoon and
86 night). Patients were asked to indicate the exact time of each meal, the name of the
87 dish, ingredients/food products it contained and the amount taken, as well as the
88 PERT dose. The FER also included a household measure table with equivalences in
89 grams and an example of a completed food record, both in order to help participants
90 to register everything the most accurate way. The food record is the regular tool to
91 assess dietary intake in all the centres, so all the patients were familiar with its use.
92 Regarding the specific FER for this study, dieticians were the personnel in charge of
93 explaining it to the patients and their families according to a common consensus
94 criterion among the centres. Patients were advised to follow their normal diet and to
95 take their regular enzyme doses.

96 The nutritional composition databases used for the energy and nutrient intake
97 calculation were purchased from EuroFIR® (Spain, Italy, Portugal, and Netherlands),
98 and Nubel® (Belgium), since they were country specific and contained the nutritional
99 facts of the particular food products in each region. Calculations were automatically
100 performed by the system through the specifically developed calculation tools. The

101 total daily energy intake was calculated and expressed as kcal/kg/day. Macronutrient
102 intake was calculated in grams of lipids, carbohydrates and protein per day and
103 expressed as percentage of total daily energy intake. The dosage of PERT was
104 evaluated by considering the Enzyme/Substrate ratio (E/S) as the unit of dosage
105 quantification, which was calculated as lipase units (LU) per gram of dietary fat (g
106 fat) per meal (LU/ g fat/ meal). Additionally, the dose was calculated in terms of LU
107 per kilogram of body weight per day (LU/kg/day) and reported as mean daily intake
108 (LU/day).

109

110 **2.4. Comparison to current recommendations**

111 All data were compared according to the recommendations of the new nutritional
112 guidelines for CF for nutritional status, energy and macronutrient intake and PERT
113 dose ⁷. The recommended value for the nutritional status indicators HFA, WFA and
114 BMI SD-scores is 0 SD, which corresponds to the mean value of an age-matched
115 healthy population. The current recommendation for total energy intake is 110-200%
116 of the recommended energy intake of healthy age-matched population. For
117 macronutrient intake the recommendations are 20% of total daily energy intake from
118 protein, 35-40% from lipids, and 40-45% from carbohydrates. Recommended PERT
119 dose is between 2.000 and 4.000 LU/g of dietary fat and below 10.000 LU/kg/day.

120 Analysis of energy intake considered the mean energy intake minus the lower
121 recommended limit (110%) to evaluate if patients were at least fulfilling the lowest
122 recommendation: 0 means the recommendation is achieved whilst negative values
123 mean the patient has achieved a lower intake than the recommended.

124 In order to classify patients according to the enzyme dosage
125 recommendations, three groups were established according to their mean daily

126 PERT intake: below the recommended range (<2.000 LU/g), within the
127 recommended range (2.000-4.000 LU/g) and above the recommended range
128 (>4.000 LU/g). Intra-patient variability in the E/S ratio intake was assessed; this
129 value expresses the spectrum of enzyme dosage for a certain amount of fat used by
130 the patient at a concrete mealtime along the 4 days record.

131

132 **2.5. Statistical analyses**

133 The sample size was estimated using Monte Carlo simulations assuming
134 normally distributed variables and aiming for a precision of $\pm 10\%$ for each variable.
135 The estimations for performing the simulations were based on data from Schall,
136 Bentley and Stallings (2006) ⁶.

137 The data were summarized using mean (standard deviation) or median
138 (interquartile range) in the case of continuous variables and with relative and
139 absolute frequencies in the case of categorical variables. The association between
140 nutritional status, age, pancreatic insufficiency, diagnosis through neonatal screening
141 (NBS) and time lapsed from diagnosis till the present study was assessed using
142 linear mixed models, adding the centre as a random effect. The Pearson correlation
143 coefficient was calculated to assess age effect on SD-scores of BMI, HFA and WFA.
144 Beta regression mixed models were used for the nutrient intake analyses. For the
145 analyses on PERT-dosage, for each patient (4 days each, 6 meals/day) the mean
146 daily dosage was calculated together with the standard deviation of the mean per
147 patient representing the intra-patient variability. A p value ≤ 0.05 was considered
148 statistically significant. 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) were provided for all
149 estimates. The statistics' analyses were performed using R software (version 3.3.2).

150

151 **3. RESULTS**

152 A total of 207 paediatric patients with CF from 6 different participating
 153 European CF centres were enrolled. **Table 1** shows the patients' characteristics
 154 according to centre. There was a slight predominance of male patients (53.3%). Only
 155 33% of the patients had been diagnosed through new born screening (NBS), with
 156 remarkable differences among centres. Ninety-one per cent of the patients suffered
 157 from PI.

158

159 **Table 1.** Clinical and demographic characteristics of the study cohort

160

	Lisbon (n=30)	Madrid (n=33)	Valencia (n=36)	Milan (n=30)	Leuven (n=29)	Rotterdam (n=49)	TOTAL (n=207)
Mean age, years (SD)	10.6 (4.8)	7.6 (5.9)	8.4 (5.1)	7.9 (5.5)	8.2 (5.7)	7.1 (4.0)	8.3 (1.2)
Male % (n)	43.3 (13)	60.6 (20)	50 (18)	63.3 (19)	62.1 (18)	46.2 (24)	53.3 (112)
Newborn screening, % (n)	0 (0)	72.7 (24)	13.9 (5)	90.0 (27)	3.4 (1)	23.1 (12)	32.9 (69)
Mean age at diagnosis (years) (SD)	2.5 (3.0)	0.1 (0.2)	1.3 (2.0)	0.4 (1.8)	0.6 (1.0)	1.0 (2.5)	1.1 (1.0)
Pancreatic insufficiency % (n)	90.0 (27)	81.8 (27)	100 (36)	100 (30)	100 (29)	80.8 (42)	91.0 (191)

161 *SD*, standard deviation

162

163 **3.1. Nutritional status**

164 **Figure 1** shows the median values of anthropometric parameters (BMI, WFA,
 165 HFA in SD-scores) and their relative positions as compared to the age-matched

166 healthy population (0 SD) for the different centres. First quartiles for BMI and HFA,
 167 (i.e. 25% of patients) were between 0 and -1SD except from one centre (Valencia,
 168 BMI), and third quartiles (i.e. 75% of children) for the three indicators were
 169 comprised between 0 and +1 SD in all centres (except for Milan, WFA). Some
 170 patients (33.5%) had a SD-score < 0 for the three parameters, but only 4 patients
 171 had SD values < -2 SD for all of them. No correlations were found between any of
 172 the parameters (BMI, HFA or WFA) and age and no statistically significant
 173 differences were found among the centres for any of the parameters.

174 Being diagnosed by NBS, was not associated with a significantly better
 175 nutritional status outcome, in terms of BMI, WFA and HFA, when considering both
 176 age of diagnosis and time since diagnosis. The nutritional status of patients with PS
 177 was similar to that of the children with PI in terms of mean SD-scores (mean SD-
 178 scores for HFA $p=0.65$, 95% CI [-0.353, 0.537]), WFA $p=0.43$, 95% CI [-0.246,
 179 0.587]) and BMI $p=0.44$ [-0.239, 0.564]).

180

181 **Figure 1.** Boxplots of anthropometric parameters in the different CF centers: BMI SD-scores, HFA
 182 SD-scores and WFA SD-scores. BMI: body mass index for age; HFA: height for age; WFA: weight for
 183 age
 184

185 3.2. Energy and Nutrients intake

186 Overall, the mean daily protein intake varied from 10% to 17% of the total
187 daily energy intake with a mean consumption of 14% (**Figure 2A**), not reaching the
188 recommendation of 20%. The mean value of carbohydrate intake was 51% (**Figure**
189 **2B**), with mean values for all centres above the recommended range. Altogether, the
190 mean lipid intake of all centres was close to the lower threshold (34%) and ranging
191 between 27-38% of the total daily energy intake. Only 3 centres fulfilled the
192 recommendation for lipids (**Figure 2C**).

193 Overall, the recommended lower limit of daily energy intake was not reached
194 by 46% of the patients. **Figure 2D** represents the mean value and 95% confidence
195 interval of the daily energy intake per centre as compared to the lowest
196 recommendations. For all the centres the mean value was slightly higher than the
197 recommendation (+50kcal). However, the mean energy intake in two centres, those
198 with the highest carbohydrates consumption and the lowest lipids consumption, was
199 found to be 20-200kcal lower than the recommended intake.

200 Age was significantly associated with the percentage of nutrients' intake in all
201 the centres: mean carbohydrate consumption decreased with age ($p<0.001$) by 1.1
202 to 2.5% per year, while mean lipid consumption increased ($p<0.001$) 0.8 to 2.2% a
203 year and protein 0.7-1.8%. There were no differences between PS and PI patients
204 regarding nutrient or energy intake.

205

206

207 **Figure 2.** Mean values (with 95% confidence interval) of macronutrients intake as percentage of total
 208 daily energy intake: carbohydrates (2A), protein (2B) and lipids (2C). Vertical dotted lines represent
 209 the recommended intake range or value; vertical line represents the mean value of all the centres.
 210 Total daily energy intake (2D) represented as mean daily energy intake per patient minus the
 211 minimum amount recommended (110% from the recommendation in an age-matched healthy
 212 population).
 213

214 **3.3. Use of PERT**

215 The mean PERT dose (LU/g fat/meal) differed widely between meals and
 216 centres. **Table 2** shows that the majority of patients in all centres either exceeded or
 217 did not reach the advised range: up to 82.7% of patients in one centre took more
 218 enzymes than recommended, while in other centres up to 75% of patients had a
 219 PERT dose lower than 2.000 LU/g fat/meal. The percentage of patients fulfilling the
 220 recommended dose ranged between 13.8 and 46.6%. Considering the dose of
 221 PERT as referred to kg of body weight, patients in one centre exceeded the
 222 maximum recommended limit of 10.000 LU/kg/day, with a mean (SD) intake of
 223 16.641 (10.568) LU/kg/day. The doses for the centres below the recommendations
 224 spread from 3.200 (1.871) LU/kg/day to 8.715 (2.199) LU/kg/day.

225

226 **Table 2.** Doses of PERT in the study cohort

	Lisbon	Madrid	Valencia	Milan	Leuven	Rotterdam	TOTAL
	(n=30)	(n=33)	(n=36)	(n=30)	(n=29)	(n=49)	(n=207)
Mean (SD) LU/kg/day	3200	5795	3206	8715	16641	5523	7144

			(1871)	(1313)	(2346)	(2199)	(10568)	(3714)	(6801)
Mean	(SD)	LU/g	1562	3616	1559	4362	7858	4209	3805
fat/meal			(802)	(4974)	(1347)	(1477)	(5027)	(5482)	(4365)
Mean (SD)		LU/day	94081	189750	86364	236375	394655	135306	182200
			(60313)	(105476)	(65386)	(159745)	(230324)	(88090)	(168533)
Enzyme supplements			1.000*		1.000*				
preparation (LU)			5.000**	5.000**	5.000**			5.000**	
			10.000	10.000	10.000	10.000	10.000	10.000	
				25.000	25.000	25.000	25.000	25.000	
							40.000		
Patients	<2.000	LU/g	70	42.4	75	3.3	3.5	24	17.3
with	of lipids								
PERT	2.000-4.000		30	14.4	19.4	46.6	13.8	42	16.8
dose	LU/g of lipids								
(%)	>4.000	LU/g	0	15.2	5.6	50	82.7	34	65.9
	of lipids								

227 *PERT* pancreatic enzyme replacement therapy; *SD* standard deviation; *LU* lipase units

228 *Capsules prepared in the Pharmacy Unit of the hospital, especially for children <1-2 years.

229 ** Pancreatin granules (1 measuring scoop = 5.000 LU)

230

231 Overall, when considering main meals (breakfast, lunch, dinner) as compared
232 to snacks (**Figure 3a**), enzyme doses or E/S (LU/g lipids) had a similar pattern, i.e.
233 doses at snacks were not higher than at main meals or vice-versa. Considering
234 different meals individually, there was not a common trend or pattern in enzyme
235 doses, neither among patients from the same centre, or when comparing different
236 centres. However, for some meals, mainly snacks, no enzymes were taken even
237 though the meal contained lipids (data not shown in **Figure 3a** since minimum value
238 represented is 250 LU/g of lipids). The upper outliers of E/S values were found at
239 snack meals in all centres.

240 Age was not associated with PERT dosage at any centre except in Valencia,
241 where the oldest children had the highest E/S values ($p < 0.01$) and in Rotterdam
242 where, on the contrary, the oldest patients had the lowest E/S ($p < 0.01$).

243 Large differences in E/S ratios among meals for the same patient (intra-
244 patient variability) were obtained, ranging from mean values of 400 LU/g of fat in
245 some meal types to 3200LU/g of fat in others (**Figure 3b**). No concrete meal type
246 was significantly associated with a higher or a lower intra-patient variability in E/S,
247 but snacks meals were the only ones showing cases of 0 variability. Centres with
248 lower E/S ratios had the lowest intra-patient variability. Finally, age was not
249 associated with intra-patient variability in E/S ($p > 0.05$) in all the centres.

250

251
252

Figure 3. Dose of PERT per meal type and centre. Expressed as mean (E/S in LU/g fat) in Figure A and expressed as intra-patient variability (SD E/S) in Figure B.

253 B, breakfast; S1, snack 1; L, lunch; S2, snack 2; D, dinner; S3, snack 3. Horizontal lines indicate the
254 recommended range for dose in terms of lipase units per gram of fat (2000-4000 LU/g fat) according
255 to Turck et al. 2016.
256

257

258 **4. DISCUSSION**

259

260 Through the present study we have characterized nutritional status, energy
261 and nutrients intake and meal-specific use of PERT of a European group of
262 paediatric patients with CF compared to what is recommended by the new guidelines
263 on nutrition in CF ⁷.

264 Firstly, we have found a very wide range of intra-centre variability in terms of
265 SD-scores for BMI, height and weight for age, with the majority of the results
266 standing between 0 and -1SD. Severe malnutrition (values < -2SD ⁷) indicators were,
267 however, found only occasionally. Association between diagnosis by NBS and better
268 outcomes of nutritional status, as previously reported in wider series ^{1,4}, was not
269 found in our study population with only 33% diagnosed by NBS.

270 Secondly, the study has pictured centre-specific macronutrients distribution
271 and energy intakes. In general terms, protein intake was lower than recommended in
272 all centres, none of which achieved the daily intake objectives; this fact could
273 possibly be explained by CF teams still applying the previous recommendations ¹⁰,
274 although not completely compliant with these neither.

275 With regard to lipids, some centres more successfully accomplished
276 recommendations than others, probably due to the higher amounts of oil and fats
277 consumed related to the local nutritional habits. Of note, centres with the highest
278 carbohydrate intake had the lowest lipids and energy intake and vice-versa. Our
279 results are comparable to those of a previous multicentre study conducted in the US
280 in infants and toddlers with CF, that showed an intake of 33.8% of energy from fat,

281 55.8% from carbohydrates and 12.4% from protein, and only 50% achieving the
282 minimum energy recommendation ¹¹. However, the mean energy intake of the whole
283 group was slightly above the 110% limit, evidencing that despite almost half of the
284 patients not complying with it, they were very close to the recommendation. This is
285 clearly reflected in Figure 2D: there is one single centre contributing to the low
286 overall value, while the mean energy intake in four centres is higher than the mean
287 of the group and than the minimum recommended. In another study carried out in
288 the US, 86 subjects aged 6.0-8.9 years had around 37% of fat intake and the 120%
289 energy goal was not reached by 61% of the children ⁶. In addition, in a larger
290 population of 234 Dutch children aged 0-18 years fat intake represented 34-36 % of
291 total energy, which in turn was 88 to 119% of recommendations for an healthy age-
292 matched population ¹².

293 Finally, our results have evidenced the lack of uniformity in PERT dosage
294 among the centres, E/S ratios ranging from mean values of 1520 up to 7758 LU/g
295 fat/meal with considerable differences among centres. In terms of maximum
296 recommended daily dose, only in one centre patients exceeded the maximum
297 recommended dose of 10000 LU/kg/day whilst in others the mean value was far
298 below. Despite this fact, no cases of fibrosing colonopathy were reported in any of
299 the centres. This is in accordance to a previous study showing that 10000 LU/kg/day
300 should not be any longer a restriction¹³, although the new guidelines maintain this
301 figure as the maximum recommended. We believe the outstripping result in one
302 centre is related to the enzyme supplements preparation of 40.000 LU recently
303 instituted. Likewise, the formulation of 1.000 LU available in the centres with the
304 lowest PERT doses may be the reason for this finding. The mean value of the whole

305 group (7.144 LU/kg/day) was, however, very similar to that reported in a Dutch
306 population (7.627LU/kg/ day) ⁴.

307 A comprehensive study in children 8-11 years assessing adherence to PERT
308 concluded that 88% of the patients were within the previously recommended range
309 of 500-4000LU/g fat and only 4% were below ⁶. According to our results, in some
310 centres very high percentage of patients were below the new recommended PERT
311 dosage range (<2000 LU/g), but if we take into account the 2002 guidelines (lower
312 limit of 500 LU/g fat), we would find a similar percentage of patients under the lower
313 limit as the previous study ⁶. We highlight the fact that despite the very wide range of
314 PERT intake (overdosing vs. underdosing) between centres, no differences were
315 found in terms of nutritional status. There was no association either between PERT
316 dose and energy intake. On the other hand, it is well known that there is an
317 enormous variability in the response to PERT among patients; in a large
318 retrospective study in children with CF no correlation was found between enzyme
319 dose and the degree of fat malabsorption ¹³. It is also possible that differences would
320 have been found when gastrointestinal complaints were taken into account.

321 The discrepancies in PERT dosing criteria found in our study reinforces the
322 absence at the present time, of a well-established and evidence-based adjustment
323 method. The authors of the new guidelines acknowledge this insufficient evidence
324 for the recommended PERT dosage, and some studies have highlighted the need of
325 conducting research in order to improve PERT adjustment ^{14,15}. Other authors also
326 highlight the need to investigate individual factors, such as gastric emptying time or
327 intestinal transit time, and inherent-to-food factors, like physicochemical
328 characteristics of the food matrix or the type of fat, as determinants on the efficiency
329 of the pancreatic enzymes supplements ¹⁶⁻¹⁹.

330 Overall, the results of this study could have an impact on daily clinical practice
331 in terms of nutritional advice and education to parents. We observed a change in
332 macronutrients distribution with age in all centres. The younger the patient, the
333 higher the carbohydrates intake (exceeding the daily recommendations), but as
334 children got older, the percentage of energy intake from carbohydrates decreased in
335 favour of an increase in that from protein and lipids. A similar tendency was
336 previously reported in a cohort of Spanish patients by Calvo-Lerma et al 2015 (PO-
337 AHP-0006 ESPGHAN 48th meeting). Higher carbohydrates intake and lower protein
338 as compared to the recommendations was also observed in another study with a
339 population aged 7-35 months¹¹. Thus intervention to promote adequate dietary
340 patterns should start at early age.

341 Moreover, the high intra-patient variability for specific meals and regarding the
342 enzyme to substrate dosage implicates that patients took a fixed enzyme dose for
343 each particular meal independently of what they ate. For example, if the child takes a
344 fixed amount of 2 enzyme capsules for breakfast each day, but the fat intake varies
345 between 10-20 g of fat, the E/S ratio would be 2.000 LU/g of fat (inside the
346 recommended range) – 1.000 LU/g (below the recommended amount). This would
347 mean an intra-patient variability of 1000 LU/g of fat between two days. These
348 findings suggest that patients should be aware and take into account the content of
349 fat in every meal in order to adjust the dose accordingly, with the target of reaching
350 the optimal/recommended E/S ratio. For this purpose educational material and
351 adequate tools should be available for patients at any time to help them to decide the
352 dose of enzymes they should take for a particular meal.

353 In this regard the results obtained, in the context of MyCyFAPP Project, may
354 be very useful. The identification of the specific nutritional imbalances to be

355 addressed and the goals established in the new guidelines will be considered as the
356 project's premises to start building up the tailored educational resources and tools
357 that eventually will be in the hand of the patient with the mobile APP.

358 The major strength of the study is the use of robust methodology that makes it
359 of scientific value, including specific and detailed food and enzyme information,
360 reliable databases and tools to calculate the nutritional facts, the common consensus
361 practice in explaining patients about how to fill in the record, expert dieticians
362 participating in the study design and its implementation, and the nature of the
363 statistical analyses performed (application of models rather than tests). Additionally
364 this is the first time, to our knowledge, that a study has been conducted that
365 specifically compares the current practice to the newly published experts' guidelines
366 in a multicentre way in 5 different European countries.

367 Our study has some limitations. Despite five European countries (6 different
368 centres) from different areas were enrolled - two northern European cities (Leuven
369 and Rotterdam) and four from the south (Lisbon, Madrid, Valencia and Milan) – the
370 conclusions may not apply to all European countries. Indeed we have found that
371 dietetic and therapeutic patterns vary from one region to another, thus future studies
372 could consider the inclusion of other countries. Although the patients completed the
373 dietary data in the food record form in detail, only a reduced number filled in the
374 specific questions about gastrointestinal symptoms and stools frequency, so those
375 data could not be used for the analyses. Besides, it cannot be ruled out that dietary
376 data recorded was totally accurate, since filling in the food record might have
377 supposed an extra burden to the patients. In the future, MyCyFAPP will provide a
378 guided and user-friendly food recording system on a mobile APP. This will improve
379 reliability and precision on the collected data. Another limitation of the study could

380 be the number of patients included; however, from the descriptive analysis'
381 perspective, which was the primary objective, the sample size was adequate.
382 Besides other studies in the field included a similar or smaller number of patients
383 ^{6,11,12}.

384 We found no association between NBS diagnosis and better nutritional
385 outcomes - as previously reported— probably due to the small sample of patients
386 applying for such analysis, and to the random nature of the inclusion criteria, only
387 32.8% of patients having been diagnosed by NBS. Moreover, the mean interval
388 between NBS until the present time was short (only 4 years), and similarly mean age
389 was low, while generally benefits from very early diagnosis and intervention is more
390 evident with age increase ¹⁹. Being pancreatic sufficient was also not associated with
391 a better nutritional status, but this sample represented only 9% of the total study
392 population. We did not study the association between nutritional status and FEV1 as
393 it was scheduled with different periodicity in the different centres, and as this was a
394 cross-sectional study, the data on FEV1 were insufficient to apply the comparative
395 analysis.

396 Our project is further studying the dietary origin of the nutrients in terms of
397 foods sources in the different countries. This knowledge will allow for advising
398 patients in a more practical way i.e. how to adjust the intake of certain products in
399 order to correct the concrete nutritional imbalances, like a deficient intake of lipids.
400 Additional information about type of lipids consumption in terms of degree of fatty
401 acids' saturation could be relevant since variations in the type of fatty acids have
402 been associated with different digestion fates ²⁰; this could affect PERT efficiency
403 and thus dosing needs. Finally, results have reinforced the need to focus the

404 research on an evidence-based method for PERT, which is being addressed in other
405 areas of the project.

406 To conclude, in a paediatric European CF population we have found
407 discrepancies between the new guidelines on nutrition along with a wide spectrum of
408 differences both in nutrients intake and PERT among the six centres. Furthermore,
409 our results proof the lack of a general criterion to adjust PERT and the potential
410 benefit of educational and self-managerial tools for patients' better adherence to
411 therapies. The development of these tools is the target of the next steps of
412 MyCyFAPP Project.

413

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485 **Legend page**

486

487 **Figure 1.** Boxplots of anthropometric parameters in the different CF centers: BMI
488 SD-scores, HFA SD-scores and WFA SD-scores. BMI: body mass index for age;
489 HFA: height for age; WFA: weight for age

490

491 **Figure 2.** Mean values of macronutrients intake as percentage of total daily energy
492 intake: carbohydrates (2A), protein (2B) and lipids (2C). Vertical dotted lines
493 represent the recommended intake range or value; vertical line represents the mean
494 value of all the centres. Total daily energy intake (2D) represented as mean daily
495 energy intake per patient minus the minimum amount recommended (110% from the
496 recommendation in an age-matched healthy population).

497

498 **Figure 3.** Dose of PERT per meal type and centre. Expressed as mean (E/S in LU/g
499 fat) in Figure A and expressed as intra-patient variability (SD E/S) in Figure B.
500 B, breakfast; S1, snack 1; L, lunch; S2, snack 2; D, dinner; S3, snack 3. Horizontal
501 lines indicate the recommended range for dose in terms of lipase units per gram of
502 fat (2000-4000 LU/g fat) according to Turck et al. 2016.

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